

On the Wrong Track?: Questioning Holm's Defence of the Expressivist
Objection Against Prenatal Diagnosis

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Introduction

Is Prenatal Testing (PNT) morally wrong? According to many disability bioethicists the answer is affirmative. One of the most important rationales against prenatal tests is that to select against disabling traits *express* a wrong moral attitude about the trait and send a hurtful message against the people with disability. This kind of argument has been labelled by Allen Buchanan the 'Expressivist' Objection –or Argument– (Buchanan, 1996) and has occupied a substantial space in the mainstream discussions of disability bioethics. Recently, Tom Shakespeare provided a powerful, systematic argument against this strategy (Shakespeare, 2006, pp. 85-102). His crucial claim is that there is nothing morally objectionable in PNT, thus we should not interpret a decision to have a termination as expressing disrespect or discrimination towards disabled people. But this seemingly conclusive criticism did not end the Expressivist Objection. In answer to Shakespeare, S. Holm characterizes three basic contexts where argument is displayed: PNT in abstraction, PNT as actual practice and, PNT as a parental choice. Since Shakespeare overlooks this distinction, some versions of the Expressivist Argument against PNT still can be held. He defends some versions and claims that this argument cannot be laid to rest. (Holm, 2008)

In this essay, I object the answer provided by Holm to Shakespeare. I will not concentrate in defending Shakespeare's critique against PNT; but I will his assume some of the basic claims he make¹. My analysis will be focused in the distinctions proposed by Holm. I will claim that the three different versions, instead being a defence of the Expressivist Objection, clarify how the argument fails in the moral discussion of disability bioethics. In this sense, I am going further than Shakespeare claiming that the argument provides no good effect and should be abandoned. In the first section of this paper, I will start with the general context of the PNT debate and the Expressivist Objection. Then I will unfold Holm' argument in second section, where I propose the distinction among the Strong, the Weak and, the Social versions of the Expressivist Objection. I proceed discuss each of them in the third, fourth and fifth section of this paper. This discussion will allow me to provide a general critic of the whole Expressivist Strategy in the sixth section. The last section is some concluding remarks.

Brief Anatomy of the Expressivist Objection Debate

PNT is a group of medical testing procedures on the pregnant woman². It basically consists in the screening certain maternal biological material (material serum or translucency) to identify the likeliness foetuses have chromosomal anomalies and other defects, such as Down syndrome, open neural tubes, and Trysome 18. Once a defect is identified, additional diagnostic testing and the possibility of abortion is offered to the pregnant women or prospective parents.

Some bioethicists have argued in favour PNT and the subsequent abortion of foetuses with disability, even suggesting that those tests are a moral duty. Representative of this view is John Harris, who claims in purely utilitarian grounds that "deliberately choosing to increase the suffering in the world when [she] could have avoided so doing" (Harris, 1998, p. 91).

On a much different side, the mainstream of disability bioethics argues a strong opposition against PNT. The most reluctant example is Adrienne Asch who since early late eighties has offered a passionate critique of the PNT, principally based in the called Expressivist Objection (Asch A. , 1990; 1999a; 1999b, Asch & Parens, 2000).

The central claim of the Expressivist Objection is that prenatal tests to select against disabling traits express a negative, discriminatory attitude or a hurtful message not only about a disabling trait, but also to people who live with those same traits (*See*, Asch A., 1999b, p. S2). The underlying idea is that the fact of testing (and subsequent abortion) *expresses* to the disabled people that 'their life is not worthy' (Saxton, 1997, p. 391) or 'we do not want you more here' (Wendell, 1996, p. 153). The objection considers that this, in several respects, is morally equal to any kind of discrimination (Asch A. 2000, p. 14). The argument has been sophisticated and particularly considers morally wrong the cases then the *single trait* of disability it is the cause of abortion. To be clear, the Expressivist Objection is *not* attempted as argument against abortion in general: PNT is wrong because it expresses something wrong against the disabled people, not because abortion is wrong. In fact, many disability theorists are pro-choice supporters.

In other word, the expressivists' claim is not that 'the practice *p* is wrong' neither the 'the practice *p* has as consequence *a* which is generally wrong'; but 'the practice *p* (and its consequence *a*) is wrong because it expresses something against *d*' (being '*p*' the practice of PNT, '*a*' the subsequent abortion, and '*d*' the disabled community).

A crucial chapter on the debate of the soundness of the Expressivist Objection was provided by Tom Shakespeare, who criticised the general position of disability bioethics and provides, what he calls, a 'liberal position' (Shakespeare, 2006). He concedes two general points to Expressivist objection: first, the argument relies on the prejudicial language used against people with disability and, more importantly, the fact that been disability as important part of the individual identity of a disabled individual.

He claims, however, that PNT is neither discriminatory nor expresses something against the disabled community. First, he thinks that preventing impairment does not necessarily send negative messages about disabled people; because, in some extent, an

impairment is not a neutral state. For some individuals, the physical trait is in fact impairment can be a real burden and thus not all the problem of disability is socially constructed.

Second, to his mind there is not evidence that material harms to disabled people result from selective abortion, and we can consider that opposite. Neither the foetus can be consider harmed because –under the gradualist position – they not moral considerable.

His main claim, in third place, is that the real problem to be discussed is the morality of abortion in general, and not the particular problem of PNT in disability. avoiding impairment it is not always morally objectionable by itself –does not 'express' something against the disabled community–, but ending life –of impaired or not impaired– foetuses is necessarily problematic. He finds troublesome that disability theorist considers hat abortion for 'social reasons' (e.g., to have enough children) and only consider abortion against disabled children morally objectionable. In any case, however, free choice plays an important role, and triumphs the particular considerations of disability bioethics. His final claim is that “[n]ot should we interpret a decision to have a test or a termination as expressing disrespect of discrimination towards disables people” (Shakespeare, 2006, p. 102).

He does not unconditionally embraces PNT: on one hand, he concedes that screening is not a duty, and, on the other hand, he criticises the near context where decision is made (in particular, the lack of information, attitude of some professionals and routinization of the practice); and, the broader social context (the ignorance of the society in general about disability and the real life of people with disability).

Unpacking Holm's distinctions

In the context of this debate, Holm provides a short argument attempting a revival of the Expressivist Objection. He claims that Shakespeare, as many opponents of the argument, misrepresents the main claims of this view. The opponents of Expressivism do

not take into account the several versions of the argument, and only focus in the stronger ones. To his mind, a difference should be made among PNT 'in abstraction', or 'as it currently exists, or as 'the individual choices made by prospective parents'³.

Holm claim that in considered in 'abstract', as Shakespeare does, choosing to terminate the pregnancy of a disabled foetus 'does not *necessarily* express a negative attitude', much less is a discriminatory practice. But interpreted in actual practice in the medical community, where the fair conditions for an adequate PNT has not yet been achieved; the Expressivist objection remains having force. He claims that 'there is, for instance, an important difference between holding that a driven politically backed social practice expresses something and holding that choices made by individual agents within the context of that practice express something'. (Holm, 2008, p. 24). He also seems to claim that if we construe the Expressivist objection, taking it in the context of the parents, they seem to lack of certain moral values. Thus taking account the distinctions, the object should not be dismissed.

Even when Holm's case is vague, we have to acknowledge an important lesson here: Shakespeare makes no difference between the several version of the disability argument (and he recognized that, *See*, Shakespeare, 2008, pp. 13-14)⁴. I will use, then, the general terms of the distinction elaborated by Holm to asses the validity of the Expressivist Objection⁵: I will refer to this distinction between the *Strong*, the *Weak* and *Social* version of the Expressivist Objection.

The *Strong Versions Expressivist Objection* is the claim that 'in abstraction' PNT is a bad practice because *necessarily express* something hurtful. The *Weak* and the *Social* captures the two other distinctions, which claim that PNT *contingently* expresses something against the disable community. While the *Weak* version refers to a set of moral reasons where the harmful message is sent, the *Social* refers to the social context. The moral reasons will be always related to parental attitude, whereas the social context will refer both the near medical context and the whole societal view. Let me examine each of these versions with more detail.

Strong Expressivist Objection

I have labelled *Strong* Expressivist Objection the position that claim that PNT, considered outside any social context or further moral considerations, *necessarily* expresses something discriminatory, hurtful, or negative against the trait or the people with trait. To be clear, the Strong Expressivist Objection does not claim that every instance of PNT or abortion is objectionable because itself; but that PNT is wrong *because* it intrinsically expressing something hurtful against the disabled community.

From the outset, the position reflects a *reduction ad absurdum*⁶. For example (following Shakespeare), the fact that people get vaccinated against polio does not reflect anything hurtful or discriminatory against the those individual who has suffered this disease neither are claiming that they have invaluable life. The same happen also if a person removes her disability: the fact that someone removes blindness by a medical procedure; it does not express something hurtful against the blind community. It would be difficult to claim, then, if a practice is not wrong, it is does not express *necessarily* express something against a group.

A different way to put it the argument express that practice *p* is wrong because it expresses something harmful to *d*. (being 'p' the practice of PNT, and 'd' the disabled community⁷). There is nothing we can do to defend this line of argument, as Holm recognizes, because it is simply unsustainable.

Weak Expressivist Objection

The *Weak* Expressivist objection claims that PNT is morally wrong because it expresses something hurtful against the community in a particular set of moral values or reasons. That is, the objection is not claiming that PNT is not necessarily expressing

something wrong, but it *contingently* expresses something harmful to the disabled community according a particular set of values that should be considered.

This weak sense of the Expressivist Objection can be held in all the different claims of discrimination or unequal treat of individuals. For example, it could argued the fact that homosexual couples cannot get formally married in certain countries (even they can have certain rights, which guarantees certain level of equal concern), certainly *expresses* something wrongful or hurtful against homosexual couples, perhaps they are that they are 'unnatural' or 'unable to procreate'⁸. Here the set of moral values are those concerning equality.

Similarly, PNT -a subsequent abortion- is wrong it not because abortion is wrong per se, but because is *express* something against the disabled individuals in a particular set of moral values. A schematic way to put the weak thesis is the following: A practice *p* is wrong because expresses something hurtful against *d* because some moral considerations *M*.

In the case of PNT, the moral considerations are always applicable to the decision of the parents, as the relevant moral agents in the decision but those reasons are not limited to discriminatory attitudes. *M* is always a set of values that the parents should abide or refrain to contradict. I will refer only to the main versions of the argument, that is, the 'discriminatory' variant; and a more subtle concern related to the moral values of parenthood. This is, indeed, a different way to put 'Parental Attitude' argument⁹.

The *discriminatory* variant of the Expressivist Objection refers to a discriminatory trait in the decision of the prospective parents. The basic claim is that the parents display a discriminatory message when they use PNT and abort *particularly* disabled children and not other children. For example, *ceteris paribus*, a disabled foetus will be aborted and not an extremely talented foetus; and this is discriminatory considering that both of them will be burdensome in some extent to their families. This has been called as Synecdochal Argument¹⁰ and claims: "As with discrimination more generally, with prenatal diagnosis, a single trait stands in for the whole, the trait obliterates the whole. With both discrimination and prenatal diagnosis, nobody finds out about the rest. The tests send the

message that there's no need to find out about the rest". (Asch & Parens, 2000). PNT is problematic when is used only to look for disability traits, expressing a discriminatory against. *M* is a demand of equality that hold that there is a special discriminatory practice against disabled people, and makes wrong some particular stances of *p* which expresses that discriminatory message.

The second variant concerns to the *parental attitudes*. This weaker variant expresses not a discriminatory behaviour *per se*, but a *negative* attitude instead. In this version *M* is a particular set of moral duties to which the parents are obliged to abide. This sets of values are, for example, the virtues of 'good parenting' (Macintyre, 1999) or the 'unconditional devotion and acceptance' (Asch & Wasserman, 2005). This set of duties claims that, since disability is part of the identity of a human being, parents should not reject their children because of any feature of their identity (sex, hair color, talents), including disability. Then, the prospective parents who decide to screen the foetus looking for disabilities fails in fulfilling their duties as parents. This particular failure makes immoral some particular stances of *p*, which expresses something hurtful against the disabled community. In this second version, then, *M* is a particular set of moral virtues and attitude concerning parenthood.

The critics show that PNT is not a praiseworthy practice. There both versions of moral reasons *M* show that, in fact, PNT is morally suspicious against the disabled community. But we cannot claim that expresses something is morally discriminatory or harmful in virtue another set of moral reasons. We have to take into account the whole problem in moral problem –abortion- and the other possible moral arguments available.

Let me consider these available arguments that the two versions of the weak Expressivist objection do not take into account. First, we agree with Shakespeare that the whole problem in the stake is problem of abortion in general, and not only the abortion of impaired children. If something is wrong in PNT is the abortion and the ending a foetal life, and not the message against the disable community.

Second, following from this construction of the argument, all moral factors should be considered. The only factor to be considered is not only the situation of disabled

people, but also other moral reasons such as the right of the women, certain justificatory moral reason as people lacking resources or rape. For example, low-income people can refrain of having a disabled foetus, and there is nothing morally objectionable in that. We cannot plausibly claim they are being discriminatory or failing as parents, because a different set of moral reason are applied here.

Third, there is a sense of certain theoretical imperialism in the Expressivist objection: that is, the only valuable rights are the rights of the disabled community, and those triumph other moral considerations. The rights of the disabled people are not more important; for example, say rights or women, prospective parents or poor people. There is a subtle balance of rights here, but the discrimination against the disabled is only one more factor to be considered.

The parental virtues variant is more flexible but does not escape of those criticisms. It could be argued that represents a too demanding view about parenthood. Further, following Gedge, the requirements of 'unconditional acceptance and devotion' overlooks some other rights of the parents (such for self-respect) it overlooks the moral requirements on children of reciprocity and mutuality. (Gedge, Forthcoming) Few people are willing to accept 'the good parenting' or the 'unconditional devotion and acceptance' as appropriate model for parenthood.

Finally, the two versions of the claim fail to recognise the important factor of *free choice* as a moral right, which is a crucial factor in all the decision concerning reproductive concerns. It is true that we have to take into account that the consequences of one's action that can harm others, but it does not eliminate the free choice. This right will allow balancing all the consideration at the stake all will to adapt to the particular situation. As Guilliot claims, whether one thinks that prenatal testing and selective abortion is commendable or right, each pregnant woman or each set of prospective parents should have access to prenatal testing and be allowed to make her or their own decision about whether to utilize the testing (and what to do test results). Freedom of choice, Gillott says, is denied if testing and abortion are not available (Gulliot, 2001). And not all the cases, will express something against the disabled community.

In sum, we can provide the general structure of our argument against the weak version. The structure of the claim is the following: The Expressivist Objection claims that that p is morally wrong because it expresses something against d because a moral set of reasons M . The moral reason M is that either/both that we are treating different one group in due their trait (discrimination) or parents are failing a particular duty (parental virtues). However, there are also moral reasons \emptyset that undermine M . \emptyset comprises all the moral reasons, in particular, those reasons that are not related to the rights of the disabled community, including the feminist conception rights of the women and the right to free choice. Because of \emptyset , the weak version fails.

The Social Context in the Expressivist Objection

A different story should be told in the case of the *Social* version of the objection. The Social variant claims that PNT is morally wrong because it expresses something hurtful against the community in particular 'social context'. I will use social context to cover the two spaces related by Shakespeare: 'the near patient context' –which is basically, how the men and women experience their pregnancy; and the 'broad cultural context' –which is the cultural and social attitudes against disability. (Shakespeare, 2006, p. 100-101)

Both Expressive supporters and detractors will agree that the 'near patient context' is objectionable because there is not enough information about the disability, the medical jargon is full with discriminatory terms, some counsellors provide negative information about disability, and there is a whole prejudice against disability. The cultural context is not better. The general population lacks of information about what is disability and how the disabled people can have a successful life and indeed, there is a general attitude against the disabled people in virtue of this ignorance.

This sociological criticism, in its near and broad variants is, in deed, the main focus of the Expressivist Objection. Holm claims to be criticising the 'actual' or 'current'

practices (Holm, 2008, p. 25). We can see this characteristic more clearly in the seminal paper by Adrienne Asch, where devotes several pages to criticise the how 'context' is what 'frames the discussion'. She denounces an story of 'outright', 'pervasive', and 'invidious' discrimination from academics, medical professionals, bioethicists, and the community in general, with detailed examples. (Asch, 1999b, S8-S14). She emphatically claims that 'the motivation of the disability critique is the *reality* of using prenatal testing and selective abortion to avoid bringing to term foetuses that carry disabling traits¹¹' (Id. S-14). Furthermore, in recent paper focused the Expressivist Objection is shows the incompatibility between the disability studies and PNT because of the 'current social practices' and the 'social context'. (Asch A., 2003).

It is clear, then, that the *true* critic against PNT is empirical, and nor moral. Since PNT is *not* intrinsically or contingently morally wrong; what it is being is the *current* practice of the PNT and the social culture where it is displayed. Let me explain my claim with the whole formulation of my argument: The Expressivist Objection, in general, claim that the practice p is wrong because it expresses something harmful to d in the social context S under the moral reasons M and \emptyset (being ' p ' the PNT; ' d ' the disabled community, and ' S ' both the near context of medical practice and the whole societal context, ' M ' the particular set of reasons and ' \emptyset ' our answers to the moral objections including freedom of choice). Answering the strong and weak version, we have proved that neither p is wrong nor expresses something against d . Furthermore, M is not conclusive against p : while \emptyset , all things considered, proves that there is nothing decisive objectionable against p -even when p is morally suspicious.

The only issue remaining is the societal consideration S , which is an empirical claim. The problem is that Expressivist Objection is presented as a moral argument against p –a moral argument about a practice, but a moral argument anyway– and when actually is an empirical critique about the state S , the context in which p is developed. This is a subtle but an important distinction: A more adequate strategy supporting d should be an *empirical* argument against conditions S –for example, a policy critique-, and not *moral* argument against p .

To be clear, the empirical criticism is based in moral grounds. The expressivists object the practice because it is at odds with certain moral considerations; that is, *S* is wrong because it fails to fulfill an aspect of *M* (basically, equality). But we cannot claim that *p* is wrong because *S* is at odds with a set of values *M*, neither expresses something. Vaccinating children against polio is not wrong because the current society discriminates people with polio (the proper objective of criticism should be the discriminating society, not the vaccine).

Finally, we can forget the complication that is to say that *p* is wrong because it 'expresses' something bad in the context *S*, not because itself. This is further more complicated claim that dilutes more the actual intention, which is to criticize *S*.

Questioning the Expressivist Objection

The former is not a trivial conclusion. First, disability bioethics gains validity with the quality of the description or critique it provides from the reality, and loses explanatory and critical potential if focus in the wrong issues. The more unfocused the debate becomes; the easier for clinicians, policy and law-makers, and even for philosopher to ignore the valid elements of disability critique, and regard them merely rhetorical, ideological and emotive claims.

The burden of disability bioethics is to pursue for a non-discriminatory society and improve services for disabled people and their families 'undercovering' the disability as a real moral and social problem. It has been successful to overcome the medical paradigm, raising the personal experiences of disabled people as the primary source of knowledge regarding disability. Further, it has achieved to identify disability as a social problem that should be dealt with through social interventions, not only an individual problem that was to be dealt with through medical intervention. But to mix moral and social considerations is not a suitable strategy to do the desired criticisms.

Second, my distinction allows showing how some alleged incompatibilities are only apparent. It is not incompatible to seek to prevent impaired children coming to the world, and also to support the rights of the existing disabled people (Favouring Buchanan, 1996; Shakespeare, 2006; Against Asch A., 2003) The real divergence is *not* about the conditions M and \emptyset , because supporter and critics often agree in both arguments. For example, expressivist and their critics both recognise free choice, the right to abortion and concede that a discriminatory exists. Since the objection and claim is about S , a somebody could coherently support p or accept a , but at the same time recognize that S is wrong.

Third, and, more importantly, it allows to show to solve the apparent tension between disability bioethics and other studies. The special disability bioethical reasons M are compatible with \emptyset , as long both recognize that the status of S is wrong. To claim that M triumph over \emptyset ; will be to claim that disability moral concerns triumph the right of the women or free choice –and nobody is willing to defend that position. More importantly, there is no need to hold p , embrace moral reasons M (or an opponent of criticise \emptyset) to recognise that the situation of S is objectionable.

The fact that the Expressivist Objection has a modest aim does not affect my claim. The objection is modest because never pretended to eliminate PNT, but only to challenge about the moral consequences of the decision. In one sense, the argument is successful because conducted to philosophers and clinicians to question about one problem; but in the other it was a failure because it made think about the wrong one.

Finally, I would like to make clear that PNT is morally suspicious. It is not something unconditionally praiseworthy and, in fact, a difficult decision for the prospective parents. However, it does not imply that it is morally wrong. I think that I helped to clarify that PNT is *not* the problem of disability, neither is morally problematic. The real moral problem is abortion. Then, the Expressivist Objection is an unsound strategy against PNT. The only context that the Expressivist Objection could be held as a moral argument is to held that the practice of abortion is not itself wrong in particular circumstances (i.e., rape); but that the women or prospective parents which make an

abortion –of a disabled or non-disabled child- are sending a hurtful message not only against other children or parents, but against the whole humanity (or if you wish, against 'sanctity' of the human life). But this is also an unsustainable argument.

Conclusion

We cannot get anything conclusive from the Expressivist Objection. Holm's clarifications do not help to support the Objection, but they do exactly the opposite. I think I have proved that the distinctions show that the objection is unsound, both in its Weak, Social and Strong version. Indeed PNT is morally suspicious; but it does not express anything morally wrong; it may 'sound' bad, but it is not really bad. I further have demonstrated that the main point of the Objection is criticising an empirical claim, and not the moral status of an action. Then, the Expressivist Objection is not a good strategy for disability bioethics because it loses explanatory power and critical power. It could be the case that the whole objection should be laid to rest.

¹ First, I will assume his discussion about abortion. Shakespeare develops a short but compelling argument about abortion, assuming a gradualist position to overcome the problem between the liberal and conservative position on abortion. (*See*, Shakespeare, 2006, pp. 92-94). I will thus consider as a permissible moral abortion those which end the pregnancy during first or second trimester of pregnancy. I agree with Shakespeare that during this time, the foetus still does not have enough moral status; but after that is enough for independent living, so it ending its life should have a different moral status. Second, I will also take his claims that there is nothing strictly 'eugenic' with PNT nor PNT is a menace the future existence of people with disabilities. Finally, being a supporter of the rights of disabled people, I have to agree with him that disability could be in fact a real burden with some individuals.

² Prenatal diagnosis, prenatal testing and prenatal will be used considered synonyms for the purposes of this paper. My argument does not include preimplantation genetics, which is a really different practice.

³ This is not the only distinction he proposes. He also claims that we must differentiate between the 'discriminatory attitude' and the 'negative attitude'. The first one is a pure act of discrimination, while the second takes into account more subtle harms, given that disability is part of one's identity, the affection that a person feels. (Holm, 2008, p. 24) We will not use it directly, but we will take it into account in our explanation.

Finally, he also makes further distinction between the intended message of utterance and justified claim that the witness can perceive. He uses the example of burning a flag. He claims that even when someone uses burning conveying a purely artistic meaning, without any clarification it would be justifiable to interpret this patriotic offence. This line of argument has the problem of what does conveying a meaning work. James Lindemann Nelson has previously discussed this problem, (Lindemann Nelson, 2000) so I will not consider this argument.

⁴ In justice to Shakespeare, we should be aware that he correctly makes several distinctions, for example, between consequentialist and non-consequentialist versions of the Expressivist objection (Shakespeare, 2006, p. 96. For some further distinctions in answer to Holm, see 2008, p. 14)

⁵ The labels were not developed by Holm. Furthermore, and it is not clear what he considers 'strong' or 'abstract'. I have interpreted his claims and labelled for the purposes of my argumentation.

⁶ A similar formulation in (Edwards, 2004)

⁷ We are assuming that '*d*' is an actual person that is harmed. I am assuming this point for the sake of the argumentation. Shakespeare, however, will disagree with this point.

⁸ A cautionary notice is needed here. It is clear, however, that all the situations around PNT and abortion are *sui generis* and it is difficult to find suitable examples.

⁹ The "parental attitude" objection is traditionally considered as a different argumentative strategy against PNT (Asch A. , 1999). For Holms and Shakespeare, however, seems to be part of the same strategy and apparently always come together.

¹⁰ Synecdoche is the label given by Erik Parens. (Asch & Parens, 2000)

¹¹ The italics are ours.

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